

Prevention of Relapse/Reoccurrence and Preparedness of a Post COVID -19 Pandemic in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the preventive measures of relapse/reoccurrence and preparedness of a post COVID 19 outbreak among individuals in Cross River State of Nigeria. The study made use of both primary and secondary data; one-on-one interview was conducted by the researchers and also works on covid-19 were assessed and used to gather information for the study. The study looked at the historical and origin, control and prevention of Covid-19. The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak, which originated in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, has gradually spread to over 215 countries. It was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization in March 2020. Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than 79 million cases and over 1.7 million deaths have been recorded globally as at December 29, 2020. The paper also discussed the multimodal strategy towards a long term COVID-19 control and prevention. For a successful immunization programme, there is a need to have a high rate of vaccination coverage. The study concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic is not over yet and with the emergence of new waves of the disease and other strains of viruses that could emerge in future, preparedness should be continuous to curtail the spread of the infection.

Keyword: Prevention, relapse, preparedness, post covid-19, Cross River State

Introduction

The Corona Virus pandemic is both a public health and economic emergency and has posed a devastating and painful experience which the presence of emergence pathogens can be consequential to lives and livelihood worldwide. By January 2020, WHO declared COVID-19 a Public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC), the highest alarm the organization can sound (Sylvia, 2020). The global response, however, has being a transformative moment, which had exposed our inherent deficiencies, inequalities and weakness in the face of the pandemic preparedness and response (Thomas & Stewart, 2020). COVID-19 pandemic is far from over and could yet evolve in unanticipated ways. However, one of its most important lessons will involve, Preparation, prevention and early execution, aimed as an essential tool in detecting, containing, and rapidly responding to and mitigating the spread of potentially dangerous emerging infectious diseases.

There is a multimodal strategy towards a long term COVID control and prevention. A protocol that sets up multiple barriers of protection so as not to only contain or eliminate covid-19 as a major-life threatening disease, but also in the long term prevent and limit the emergence of novel viruses and a return to a new socioeconomic life. It is important because of the likelihood that COVID will become endemic (Lavine, et al, 2020).The aim therefore is to eliminating the disease from our communities, even when there are limitations to applying these same measures globally (Brookings Global working paper, August 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO)defines pandemic preparedness as “having national response plans, resources, and the capacity to support operations in the event of any pandemic”. It includes prevention, detection and containment measures, as well as programmes that respond to and mitigate issues that arise from the spread of pandemics, such as (PPE) shortages, limited hospital capacity, and acquisition of vaccines and other countermeasures (Sylvia et al, 2020).

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak, which originated in Wuhan, China, in December, 2019, has gradually spread to over 215 countries. It was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization in March 2020. Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than 79 million cases and over 1.7 million deaths have been recorded globally as

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of December 29, 2020. In Nigeria 255,937 cases have been confirmed, 249,996 cases have been discharged and 3,143 deaths have been recorded in 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory as of 19th to 20th May 2022 (NDCC, 2022). Most people who develop COVID-19 fully recover, but current evidence suggests approximately 10%-20% of people experience a variety of mid- and long-term effects after they recover from their initial illness. These mid- and long-term effects are collectively known as post COVID-19 condition or long COVID. It is important to remember that the understanding of post COVID-19 condition, along with COVID-19, continues to evolve. Researchers are working with patients who develop post COVID-19 condition to better more understand about its cause, symptoms and effects. World Health Organization update information and materials as we learn more.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a devastating effect on many countries' economies, health systems, education systems, and infrastructure. The disease presently has no cure, and disease management is mainly supportive. Regular hand washing, use of facemasks, social distancing, and cough etiquette are vigorously recommended to limit community transmission of the virus. Researchers across the world have been working assiduously to develop vaccines against the highly contagious virus (Ita, 2021). Approximately 60 COVID-19 candidate vaccines are undergoing clinical evaluations and another 172 COVID-19 candidate vaccines are at the preclinical evaluation stage as of December 29, 2020. However, there are widespread skepticism and divergent views regarding the legitimacy of the various COVID-19 vaccines among people across the globe. The pandemic has significantly impacted health systems and economies globally. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has been described as a global health pandemic that has the potential to cause unprecedented devastating socio, economic and political crises (Lone & Ahma, 2020). To stem the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, Nigeria received an estimated 4 million doses of the AstraZeneca/Oxford vaccine through the COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access (COVAX) facility, a partnership between Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunizations (GAVI), United Nation Children's Fund (UNICEF) and WHO in March 2021 (Ita, 2021). The National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA), through the State's Primary Health Care Board, commenced the vaccination of Nigerians' priority groups in March 2021, starting with frontline healthcare workers, strategic leaders, security officials and other public personnel identified as eligible for the first phase of vaccination. While the government is doing its best to ensure that most Nigerians gets vaccinated, there has been hope, fear, government distrust, hesitancy, rejection, and conspiracy theories as the COVID-19 vaccination exercise continues (Kimble; Coustasse & Maxik, 2021). Studies both globally and locally have shown that there is a diverse rate of variability in the awareness, perception, willingness, and acceptance rate of the COVID -19 vaccine (Mohammed, 2020); Cavaleri, Enzmann, Straus & Cooke, 2021; Coustasse & Maxik, 2021).

Generally, for a successful immunization programme, there is a need to have a high rate of vaccination coverage. It is important to understand the Cross-River State of Nigerian factors such as awareness, perception, and willingness to receive the vaccine especially as the first phase of the vaccination exercise kicked off with health workers and frontline personnel. It is hoped that this will guide towards planning for the subsequent phases that will involve a larger population of Nigerians.

Thrust of the Paper

The thrust of this paper is to examine the preventive measures of relapse / reoccurrence and preparedness of a post COVID 19 outbreak among individuals in Cross River State of Nigeria. This can be done through:

1. Occasional checkups to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
2. Social distancing to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
3. Regularly washing of hand and sanitizing to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
4. Regularly wearing of nose mask to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
5. Physical and environmental hygiene to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
6. Vaccine Hesitancy and COVID 19 reoccurrence
7. Peer education influence and COVID 19 reoccurrence

Occasional checkups to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence

The novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has become a major public health problem since the initial outbreak in Hubei, Wuhan, China. The pandemic has significantly impacted on health systems and economies globally. Countries with weaker health systems, particularly those in Africa, were projected to be devastated by the COVID-19. Several vaccines are presently at different phases of

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clinical evaluation. In addition, some of the vaccines have since obtained Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) from the World Health Organization (WHO) and other relevant authorities; notably, BioNTech/Pfizer (BNT162b), Moderna (mRNA-1273), Janssen (Ad26.COV2.S), AstraZeneca (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) vaccines and host of others. Since vaccination coverage is a defining factor for successful herds immunity, there is a need to explore the determinants of COVID-19 vaccine uptake that could guide effective vaccination strategies (Lone & Ahmad, 2020). However, "relapse" is the manifestation of symptoms after recovery, while recurrence is referred to infection with the same species and strain of SARS-Cov-2 that may occur due to immunodeficiency of the host. The patients with COVID-19 recurrence evidence ranged in age from 4 to 80 years old and need to repeat test to confirmed status of wellness. Hence, reoccurrence on an individual, means that a person was infected with an agent, recovered, and then become infected later. New infection can be due to a previous infectious agent or becoming infected with a new variant of the agent. According to the CDC's protocol, based on clinical recovery and discharge criteria, recovered patients should have at least one negative SARS-Cov-2 PCR result.

Globally, the virus is believed to be transmitted through droplets and contact transmission although speculations about airborne transmission exist (Anaesthesia, 2020). While research is focusing on the epidemiology, transmission, vaccine development, and therapeutics for COVID-19, there remain gaps in our understanding of the natural history of this disease. One of those gaps is the possibility of disease relapse. Patients reinfected with a strain determined to be of a different genotype or subtype than the previous strain they were infected with can easily be identified using genotyping assays. However, when relapse with a similar strain of the same subtype occurs, phylogenetic analysis is required to distinguish reinfection from a virologic relapse (Xiao & Wong, 2020). In the quest to better understand the incidence natural history of COVID-19, this systematic review of published evidence aims to identify the trends of COVID-19 relapse, the effects of comorbidities on its relapse, and relapse-associated mortality rates. Batisse, Benech, Botelho-Nevers, Bouiller, Collarino and Conrad (2020) reported that recurrence of COVID-19 after apparent recovery is increasingly globally. According to them, a Collaborative study COVID recurrences (COCOREC) proposed a COVID-19 recurrence to be considered if the second episode occurred 21 days following a symptom free period and alternative etiologies are excluded. In a study conducted by Ye, Pan, Pan, Deng, Chen and Li (2020) on clinical characteristics of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 reactivation from Wuhan China, and the authors observed that 9% (5/55 patients) had a recurrence of the disease. Both asymptomatic and minimally symptomatic patients had the potential to reactivate.

A retrospective study by Agarwal et al. (2020) who analyzed 851 SARS-CoV-2-positive patients with at least two positive PCR tests found that 99 of them remained SARS-CoV-2-positive after 28 days from their initial diagnosis date. The report showed that the median lower and upper bounds for viral RNA shedding in COVID19 patients occurred between 2 to 3 weeks. This raises serious concerns on whether a more precautionary measure should be considered in declaring the recovery phase from COVID-19 infection, and the significance of follow-up, especially in the most vulnerable population (CDC, 2021). There are still a lot of unknown clinical features related to COVID-19 epidemiology, especially in recovered patients. In this regard, it is necessary to understand the epidemiological features of RP-SARS-CoV-2 in recovered patients and to examine whether they are potential threats to public health. Several studies that reported the situations of RP-SARS-CoV2 suggested that subsequent infection mostly occurs due to reactivation or reinfection rather than testing errors or prolonged viral shedding. However, this issue needs urgent attention to investigate whether RP-SARS-CoV-2 patients could be a serious public health problem.

However, some studies such as Hansen, Michlmayr, Gubbels, Mølbak and Ethelberg (2020); Perez, Banon, Gazit, Moshe, Wortsman and Grupel (2021) reported that a small proportion (about 1%) of the population can be RP for SARS-CoV-2, and possibly due to reactivation or relapse. Furthermore, previous reports from Ravioli, Ochsner, and Lindner (2020); He and Dong (2020) highlighted that RP-SARS-CoV-2 is less likely to cause serious problems to public health since the rate of RP seems low (about 1%), and new infections declining after recovery from the first episode of the infection which is likely due to the suspected herd immunity. This suggests that previously infected individuals have a significantly lower risk of being infected for the second time. Consequently, the aforementioned studies highlighted the possibility of reactivation and/or reinfection of SARS-CoV-2, which is less likely to cause a serious public health problem. However, caution should be exercised especially for vulnerable populations even after recovery from SARS-CoV-2. Also, close monitoring on an outpatient Basis appears crucial, since the clinical features and potential reasons for possible reactivation and reinfection remained unclear.

Vaccine hesitancy and covid-19 recover

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The World Health Organization (WHO) Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization (SAGE) has described vaccine hesitancy as the delay in acceptance or refusal of vaccination despite the availability of vaccination services. Vaccine hesitancy is considered a significant threat to global health, and thus, due to regional and population variability, there is a need to explore local data to add to the global data pool on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance and hesitancy. Despite the wide availability of the COVID-19 vaccine, safety measure of COVID 19, previous experience suggests huge limitations on vaccination uptake. Sometimes, available information on the COVID-19 are misleading, resulting in confusion and overload. The unfortunate experiences from the previous pandemics (e.g., Influenza), particularly the low acceptance in many countries, suggest the need for an improved understanding of adherence to COVID 19 post condition and vaccine's hesitancy to prevent the spread or re-occurrence the pandemic. The National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) of Nigeria has approved the use of the AstraZeneca (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) vaccine for use in the country, and presently several others. The Nigerian government has received several batches of the vaccine via the COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access Facility (COVAX), a partnership between the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), Gavi the Vaccine Alliance, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Bank, and the WHO. The COVAX is part of the Access to COVID-19 Tools (ACT) Accelerator, a global collaboration to accelerate development, production, and equitable access to tests, treatments, and vaccines for COVID-19. Nigeria's National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA) has since commenced stage wise vaccination with priority groups, starting with frontline healthcare workers. The agency has also deployed a self-registration portal online to roll out a country-wide vaccination programme (Xiao & Wong, 2020).

Social distancing, regularly washing of hand and sanitizing to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence

The Federal Government of Nigeria in partner with NDCC has approved the guidelines for safety measure to prevent COVID-19 Pandemic and re-occurrence COVID-19 as the key strategies for implementing safe, efficient and equitable plans for elimination of COVID 19 in the country. The document focuses on attendance, social distancing, hygiene, cleaning, and non-pharmaceutical interventions for safe and healthy activities and programs. Fortunately, we have observed that many people not only have resisted unethical practice during this crisis, but also have proactively engaged in various COVID-19 guideline activities, particularly those that can offer immediate help and assistance to the fight against the virus. Precautionary measures to limit the spread of the virus necessitated a shift in the communication paradigm when it comes to greetings and handshakes. The arising situation required people to adopt salutations that do not entail physical contact, such as the "peace sign," the "hand on chest" and the "namaste" (Bergdahl & Nouri, 2020). Protective measures, such as social distancing, hygiene practices and face masks, are essential to mitigate efforts against the virus, but pose challenges on daily face-to-face communication (CDC, 2020).

According to UscherPines, Schwartz, Ahmed, Zheteyeva, Meza, Baker and Uzicanin (2018) the aim of safety measures are important to protect the health of our society. These include quarantines; travel restrictions; limiting travel, use of rose mask, hand sanitizer, regularly washing of hand, avoiding crowded areas, using no-contact greetings, and physically distancing themselves from others. The approaches were more on causes and remediation strategies in Nigeria. However, available justification showed that the variables mentioned above have direct impacts of COVID 19 outbreak among individuals in Cross River State which is the main focus of the study.

COVID-19: The ravaging pandemic

COVID-19 is a potentially severe acute respiratory infection caused by Severe Acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Infectious diseases such as COVID-19 have demonstrated an ability to ravage populations, overwhelm health systems and economies and destabilize governments. The WHO had reported an outbreak of a novel coronavirus(nCoV) which started in China in December 2019, and has since then spread to the rest of the world. This new strain of Coronavirus causes a myriad of symptoms which includes; fever, cough, shortness of breath and difficulty breathing; respiratory symptoms. In more severe cases infection can cause pneumonia, severe acute respiratory syndromes (SARS) and even death.

Robust strategies for domestic pandemic preparedness

A coordinated and comprehensive approach towards the prevention of relapse/reoccurrence of covid-19 requires investments to be made. Contending COVID-19 require using all available tools at our disposal, while also been aware of our

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limitations, inequities and disparities within our region which pose a challenge to mitigating the disease. Some nations have been successful so far in containing the spread through public health measures such as testing, contact tracing, and isolation of confirmed and suspected cases, vaccination and so forth, keeping the number of deaths within their territories low. The following are some of the proposed coordinated and organized strategy towards COVID-19 control in the Cross-River State:

1. Social Measures & Services
2. Safe waste management; environmental cleaning, sterilization of patient care equipment and linen.
3. Maintaining safe distancing from others (at least 1 meter), even if individual don't appear sick.
4. With the gross disparities within the country, identifying at risk populations most vulnerable to infectious conditions – like the marginalized at-risk and underserved communities and villages in the sub regions of the country inaccessible to COVID-19 preventive measures will be a moral imperative and critical dimension of the COVID-19 pandemic preparedness, response and security.
5. Sensitization, social mobilization and awareness
6. Advocacy for safer environment – Ensuring a clean and hygienic home and working place – regular disinfectant cleaning of surfaces and objects; because contaminated surfaces is one of the main ways infections spreads.
7. Advocacy for practices of cough etiquettes – maintaining social distance, cover coughs and sneezes with disposable tissues or clothing and wash hands.

Information and data sharing

With international cooperation and participation in response to COVID-19 as to our principal donor - The World Bank support and government agencies, will pave notable success. The presence of international community and government will boast both local and global development and equitable distribution of safe and effective vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics for novel coronaviruses.

Secondary prevention measures

1. As a notifiable disease: Early recognition of cases and prompt reporting to local health authorities or agencies.
2. Immediate isolation of suspected and confirmed cases and implementation of recommended and standard infection and control procedures in line with our Local protocols, including standard precautions at all times.

Areas for infections control and surveillance

1. Point of entry (POE): In line with the WHO recommendations, point of entries – State and local Government level; health facilities, especially the Primary Health Care (PHC) centres should be utilized.
2. Collaborating with Primary Health Services (PHS) on strengthening preparedness: There should be plan to re-train stakeholders and expanding intensive care capacity.
3. Reminder of the basic principles to reducing the general risk of transmission acute respiratory infections, following standard precaution measures.
4. Avoiding close contact with infected persons; frequent hand washing, cough etiquette practices for persons with symptoms of acute respiratory infection, advocating standard infection prevention and control practices within the health care facilities.
5. Identifying common signs and symptoms of communicable diseases
6. Reporting to/inform PHS of any identified cases.
7. Activating the Public Health Emergency contingency plan as necessary, in line with the country's surveillance and response.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic is not over yet and with the emergence of new waves of the disease and other strains of viruses that could emerge in future. Preparedness is a continuous process and the objective is to curtail the spread of the infection, provide a road map to better prepare and execute in future waves of the current pandemic and inevitably when the next pandemic threat emerges.

Recommendations

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1. Preventing infection and control is avoiding exposure to the virus with standard preventive measures of public health containment.
2. Public enlightenment and awareness campaigns/education: For any pandemic, disseminating information and providing regular update of its public health message is key to prevention and control.
3. Support for vulnerable groups and populations; Example women, children, elderly, individuals with chronic medical conditions etc.
4. Isolation and restrictive measures: Avoiding close contact with anyone showing symptoms of respiratory illness such as coughing and sneezing. Staying at home if sick and isolating from other people.
5. Regular and proper hand washing with soap and water, or alcohol-based sanitizers.
6. Practicing respiratory hygiene: Cover mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing, discard tissue immediately in a close bin, and wash hands. Good respiratory hygiene prevents the spread of the virus.
7. Encourage vaccination: Available safe and effective vaccines provide strong protection against serious illness, hospitalization and death for COVID-19. Getting vaccinated is a core strategy to protecting against the virus and a necessary reality of contentment helping to end the pandemic and also stop new variants emerging. Encouraging vaccination will prevent symptomatic infection and severe diseases, which is critical to controlling the spread.

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